

METHODOLOGY OF COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN INFORMATICS

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Abstract

The main outcome of school education should be its compliance with advanced development goals. This means that children should be involved in research projects, during which they will learn to invent, understand and master new things. Achieving the set goal is possible if all directions are fulfilled, the first two of which are especially relevant for the pedagogical community. Thus, the main task is the transition to new educational standards that form requirements for learning outcomes, which should include not only knowledge, but also the ability to apply it.

Keywords: informatics, methodology, teaching, competence, training results

The formation of students' ICT competence implements a system-activity approach and takes place in the process of studying all subjects of the curriculum without exception, and its result is an integrative result of training for schoolchildren. In a generalized form, this is reflected in the ICT competence formation sub-programme and the planned results of mastering the main educational program of general education.

Educational activity in the educational development system is not only the child's participation in the learning process in the classroom, but also an activity aimed at achieving internal, not external, results and primarily the development of theoretical thinking [1, p. 118–121].

Competence is the ability to apply knowledge, skills and competencies to achieve desired results. Competence is the mastery of relevant competences that include the teacher's personal attitude to himself and his subject. A competency approach is one that focuses on learning outcomes. In this case, the result of training is not the sum of the acquired information, but the ability of a person to act in various problem situations. Competency-based education is education aimed at developing students' competence [4, p. 209-214].

Thus, the problem of transition from a traditional school focused on acquiring a certain amount of knowledge to an educational system focused on personal and professional development in a rapidly changing world, which prepares future active participants in social and business life, is particularly relevant today [7, p. 757-760]. Transformations in education are conditioned by the intensification of life, the development of scientific and technical progress, the strengthening of information exchange processes, and the informatization of society as a whole. Achieving educational results meeting the requirements of social development with a new paradigm is a very complex and underdeveloped process in the modern school.

The formation of new educational goals raised the question of the most effective technologies for their implementation. The works of researchers reflect the content of new educational technologies and their application in the process of teaching informatics (2; 3, pp. 3-

10; 5, pp. 143-150, etc.), structural components of using the project method in the process of teaching informatics, stages, positive and negative aspects are defined [6].

The realities of the educational process of the modern school are such that today almost all educational subjects contain elements of the use of information technologies, therefore society allocates a special place to the science of informatics in the period of its informatization. At this stage, it is very important to have the ability to work with information quickly and efficiently, using modern tools and methods of information processing.

The study of scientific and theoretical-methodological studies shows that the problems of application of the competence-based approach and application of the project method have been studied in depth enough. However, in the studies conducted, the problem of using informatics training for the formation of basic competencies among students using electronic portfolio technology has not been sufficiently studied.

The "Know/Understand" section includes requirements for students' mastery of repeated learning material. Graduates should understand the meaning of the concepts, principles and examples studied. The "Ability" section includes requirements based on more complex types of activities, including creative activities. The title "creative application" presents requirements that go beyond the scope of a specific academic subject and are aimed at solving various life problems. It is these most important features that are the subject of our analysis. The complexity of core competencies provides an additional opportunity to present educational standards in a systematic form, allowing the establishment of clear measures to verify the success of their mastery by students.

Conversations, questionnaires and tests are conducted to determine indicators of structural components of basic competences among 10-11th grade students. Based on the results obtained at the specified stage, the transition to the second stage of the construction of the content of the educational material takes place.

The basis for its implementation is the process of analyzing the representation model of the main compe-

tencies of students in the subject "Informatics", as a result, the content of the educational material is built on the basis of the following provisions:

- the priority goal is the development of basic skills among high school students in the process of studying informatics;
- competency-based and system-activity approaches focused on action and activity as the basis of the educational process, as well as "systematic reconstruction of knowledge" to eliminate information overload and narrow topic;
- the project method as a tool implemented using "project" (problems related to non-obvious algorithm for the implementation of the final product) and "project-type tasks" (tasks with a special technological algorithm related to the topic under study to achieve a certain result) is used;
- e-portfolio technology, understood as an element of information and communication technologies, is used to improve the efficiency of the development of students' basic skills.

In the first place, there should be the ability to pose a problem before having a specific body of knowledge on the subject: to solve the problem successfully, you need to know algorithms, formulas and operators, and in the early stages of training, it is necessary to direct both the teacher and the student to their formation.

But gradually, traditional knowledge, skills and habits should take their place - the place of the internal resource of the subject for the knowledge base of the development of intelligence. Then it is necessary to develop the need and ability to think using existing internal resources, including knowledge, skills and abilities. In general, a necessary condition for the implementation of the project method and any special project is the formation of the educational situation with competencies.

Thus, we can formulate the following mandatory requirements for the project method in computer science classes:

- problematic (ie, the lack of a predefined algorithm for solving the training situation) and, as a result, the need to formulate the problem independently, that is, to transform a set of empirical data into the form of "conditions" of the problem with a certain solution algorithm;
- the variability of the solution (as in real life, there is always more than one solution, and students should be aware of this and not be afraid to justify and make mistakes - the main thing is to correct them);
- integrativeness (a project-based learning situation should go beyond the boundaries of any academic discipline, because a problem in real life seems to be connected with many factors and areas of existence - therefore, the integrative point will strengthen motivation and bring the project as close as possible to reality).

When to use project-type assignments and when to use projects. The following provisional classification of projects can be proposed here:

1. Mini-projects (suitable for one lesson). or part of a lesson).
2. Short-term projects (4-6 lessons are needed to coordinate the activities of project team members).

3. Weekly projects (performed by the group during the project week).

4. Long-term projects.

From the point of view of this classification, it is appropriate to carry out project-type tasks over time within the framework of mini-projects and short-term projects.

This is actually the period when the foundations are laid for working on projects. Long-term projects (as a rule, quarterly, semi-annually or annually) are specifically aimed at independent formulation, solution and practical implementation of the project.

It should be noted that the application of the project method in practice leads to a change in the position of the teacher. From the carrier of ready knowledge, he becomes the organizer of students' cognitive and research activities. The psychological climate in the classroom also changes, as the teacher has to direct his teaching-educational work and the work of students to different types of independent activities of students, to the priority of research, search and creative activities.

The study of the use of the project method in informatics classes showed that the project should be understood as a means of educational modeling of life situations. A distinction is made between concepts such as the project itself and project-type tasks.

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